

These algorithm and software were tested against observed data for rice communities (L.P. Lan, pers. commun. 1997); they performed well.

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Newspaper: a new attractant for golden apple snail management

R.C. Joshi and M.S. de la Cruz, Crop Protection Division, Department of Agriculture-Philippine Rice Research Institute (DA-PhilRice), Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija 3119, Philippines E-mail: joshiravi@hotmail.com

Rice farmers in the Philippines widely use synthetic commercial molluscicides against golden apple snail (GAS) *Pomacea canaliculata*, with little, if any, consideration of hazards to nontarget organisms and the environment. Other management options are seldom employed on a community basis for various reasons. Farmers report that manual hand-picking of GAS shells is back-breaking and herding of ducks after harvest and before planting produces an itch among farm workers. We studied several attractant materials, including newspaper, as potential tools to minimize human health hazards and inconvenience in managing GAS. Newspapers, not known to farmers as a GAS attractant, are easily biodegradable, readily available, and recyclable. In addition, they do not threaten plant biodiversity loss. We hope that this tool will further reduce the misuse of synthetic commercial molluscicides.

To determine the efficiency of materials that attract GAS, a series of tests was performed

from September 2000 to February 2001.

Test 1. Leaves of three plant species familiar to lowland farmers [banana (*Musa* sp.), taro (*Colocasia esculenta*), and papaya (*Carica papaya*)] and newspapers were tested as GAS attractants. Each of the four materials was sized 6 cm² for uniform coverage of field water and soil surface. Each treatment was replicated seven times in a randomized complete block design. GAS were introduced at 0700 h in the screenhouse at a density of 10 m⁻² microplot under no-choice conditions. The number of GAS attracted was recorded from 10 to 60 min, and finally at the end of 24 h.

Test 2. Materials for GAS attraction were the same as those used in trial 1, but were tested under free-choice conditions in a 2×5-m plot. Treatments were replicated four times and placed randomly in the middle of large plots. Ten GAS were released in each of the four corners of the plot. The test began at 0630 h. The number of GAS attached to the

test material at 30 min, 5 h, 10 h, 24 h, and 32 h was recorded. At the end of 32 h, the percent surface area of material consumed was also recorded.

Test 3. The same attractants were again used for trial 3, but the only difference was that fields were treated with 40–40–40 kg NPK ha⁻¹ before transplanting. The trial was replicated five times under free-choice conditions. Materials were placed at 1600 h and, at 0800 h the following morning, the number of GAS within a 1-m² circumference and those feeding on attractants was counted.

Test 4. The test was conducted at the Banaue rice terraces in Mountain Province, Philippines, where GAS is a new problem. Since papaya leaves are hard to find, trumpet flower leaves were used instead. Our past surveys indicated that the local people have been using trumpet flower leaves to attract GAS. Other attractants used were similar to those used in earlier trials. The attractants were placed at 0630 h in newly prepared fields.

Table 1. Number of GAS attracted over time to various materials in the same screenhouse under the free-choice test, DA-PhilRice, Nueva Ecija, September 2000.^a

Attractant material	Minutes					Hours	
	10	20	30	40	50	1	24
Newspaper	0.0 c (0)	0.3 b (3)	1.9 b (19)	2.4 b (24)	2.3 b (23)	2.0 c (20)	2.3 c (23)
Banana	0.0 c (0)	0.6 b (6)	0.9 c (9)	1.0 c (10)	1.0 c (10)	0.2 d (2)	0.6 d (6)
Taro	3.0 a (30)	3.0 a (30)	3.1 a (31)	3.3 a (33)	4.4 a (44)	4.2 a (42)	4.1 a (41)
Papaya	2.1 b (21)	2.9 a (29)	3.1 a (31)	3.3 a (33)	4.1 a (41)	3.3 b (33)	3.0 b (30)

^aValues in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. Numbers in parentheses are % of GAS attracted.

Table 2. Number of GAS attracted and material consumed (%) in the free-choice test, screenhouse, DA-PhilRice, Nueva Ecija, November 2000.^a

Attractant material	GAS feeding on attractant (no.)					Attractant consumed (% surface area)
	30 min	5 h	10 h	24 h	32 h	
Newspaper	1.7 a	1.2 ab	3.0 ab	2.7 b	2.0 b	25
Banana	0.7 a	0.0 b	1.0 c	1.0 c	0.0 c	50
Taro	2.0 a	1.2 ab	2.2 b	2.7 b	2.2 b	100
Papaya	2.2 a	1.5 a	3.7 a	4.0 a	3.0 a	100

^aValues in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 3. Number of GAS attracted to trumpet flower leaves compared with other materials under the free-choice test, Banana rice terraces, February 2001.^a

Attractant material	GAS attracted (no.)	
	8 h	24 h
Newspaper	3.2 b	9.1 ab
Banana	5.7 a	8.6 ab
Taro	4.8 ab	11.4 a
Trumpet flower	3.7 ab	5.6 b

^aValues in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Observations on number of GAS attached to various attractants were made 8 h and 24 h after the attractants were first placed.

In test 1, GAS was most attracted to leaves of taro, followed by papaya leaves 10 min after release (Table 1). It took a shorter time to attract GAS on taro and papaya leaves than with other test materials. After 1 h, taro leaves again had the highest GAS attraction (42%), followed by papaya leaves (33%), newspaper sheets (20%), and banana leaves (2%) (Table 1).

In the free-choice test (test 2), taro and papaya leaves attracted more GAS than banana and newspaper as shown by the number of GAS feeding on these materials at 32 h (Table 2). Taro and papaya leaves were completely consumed except for the midribs. Only 25% of the newspaper was consumed at the end of 32 h.

In test 3, GAS numbers did not differ among attractants, although the highest GAS numbers were found on papaya leaves as well as on a 1-m² circumference surrounding the attractant (data not shown).

In test 4, taro leaves had the highest number of GAS, while trumpet flower leaves had the lowest number—but statistically, this did not differ from banana leaves and newspaper. At the end of the second sampling (24 h), taro leaves were singled out as the most important indigenous material to attract GAS (Table 3).

All test materials attracted GAS but differed in the degree of attraction (Tables 1–3). We ob-

served that no-choice conditions forced GAS to consume any test material, although they took longer to consume the less preferred attractants. In areas where leaves of attractants are scarce, newspaper can be used to attract GAS in rice fields prior to crop establishment (direct seeding/transplanting). However, in fields where rice crops have already been established, taro and papaya leaves are the best GAS attractants.

NOTE

The following table was left out in the June 2001 issue of IRRN 26(1):28–29. It is part of the note titled "Testing a yield loss simulation model for rice in Chinese rice-wheat system production environments" by D. Zhu, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI), Hangzhou 310006, Zhejiang, China; L. Willocquet, CBGP, Campus International de Baillarguet, CS 30 016, 34988 Montpellier/Lez cedex, France; Q. Tang, S. Huang, X. Lin, CNRRI; L. Fernandez, F.A. Elazegui, IRRI, Philippines; and S. Savary, CBGP.

Simulated and observed grain yield (g m⁻²) in the experiment done at CNRRI in 1998.

Treatment ^a	PS2 ^b		PS6 ^b		PS7 ^b	
	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated
CTRL	422	418	579	568	787	787
WH	420	408	-	-	-	-
SHB	393	402	519	517	689	711
WEED	319	331	523	550	669	686
COMBI	361	343	509	493	611	670

^aCTRL = control, WH = white heads, SHB = sheath blight, WEED = weeds, COMBI = combination of the three injuries. ^bPS2 = reference production situation, PS6 and PS7 = production situations that prevail in Zhejiang Province.